

CUSTOMERS PERCEPTION ON ONLINE ADVERTISING

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Cite This Article: R. Mahalakshmi & D. Rajasekaran, "Customers Perception on Online Advertising", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 142-146, 2018.

Abstract:

Online advertising is a very fast moving area. The techniques and formats used to advertise are changing constantly as advertisers try to adapt to this medium. Most companies use an outside agency to help create advertising campaigns and to select and purchase media. The main objectives of the study are to know the level of customers perception on online advertisements. Convenience sampling was also used to determine the sample size for the farmers. Pollachi Taluk is the study area. A total of 250 customers are taken as sample for this study. The study makes use of statistical techniques such as simple percentage analysis and Chi-square in analyzing the data for finding the result. The study recommended that the number of companies advertising online is soaring, but even then fraud and deception may reduce consumer confidence. So, they should be ensured that products and services are described truthfully in online advertisements.

Key Words: Online Advertising, Customers Perception & Purchase Media

Introduction:

In the latest decades, one of the essential problems of Companies is the knowledge of how the consumer will respond to various things that will be used for achieving their ultimate goal. For this purpose Companies now attracts towards online advertising because online advertising has grown rapidly in the last decade. The numbers of peoples becomes very high day by day in connecting and spending more time online. The term advertising which means promotional activities of goods and services offered by the company and it is essential tool for attracting the customers. Many companies do not aware of selecting a suitable medium of advertising for their products. Recent days the internet is most popular entertainment for peoples in all over the world.

The internet users are increasing day by day due to their own interest in using the internet on the regular basis. Recent days companies are changed their advertisement medium from traditional advertisement into online advertisement. Because the online advertisement is very familiar with the customer side. Traditional advertisement mediums like Physical banners, Television, Radio were used in the earlier days for promoting the products and services of a particular company while online advertisement mediums like Webpage ads, Facebook, Twitter, Whatsapp and other various types of online advertising mediums are used by the companies. Online advertisement is top most advertisement medium for advertising products. Increase of online users they might watch the online advertisement without fail. In online advertisement it includes various types of advertising like online text ad, Banner ad, Pop-up ad, Pop-under ads, In-stream video advertisement etc., are used by the companies for promoting their products and services among the customers.

Types of Online Advertisement:

Online Text Ad: Online text advertisement is an internet advertising medium used to display an advertisement when a query matches with the advertiser keyword and it is also called as cost per click advertisements. The advertisers pay the publisher when the advertisement is clicked by the user.

Determining Cost per Click: In this, model there are two primary models such as flat rate and bid-based. The advertiser can gain from each visit when the individual person is visit the official website links.

Flat Rate Online Text Ads: In the flat rate online text advertisements both the publisher and advertiser agree upon a fixed amount for to be paid for each click. These sites are usually used to advertise a product are service categories which gives high degree of target to the advertisers.

Banner Ads: Banner advertisement is an image or a graphic that is located on the website, usually on top of the page. It has the hyperlink that links to another webpage for advertising the products or services.

Video Advertising: The term video advertising refers to online display advertisements that have video within them, but it generally occurs before, during or after a video stream on the internet.

In-Stream Video Advertising: The stream video advertising have two core video advertisements product category that is linear video advertisement and non linear video advertisement. The linear video is presented before, in the middle or after the video content is consumed by the user. The non-linear ad runs parallel to the video content and it can be delivered as text, graphical ads or as video overlays.

Review of Literature:

Juliane Sab (2011), in his study on "Online Advertising in the Tourism Industry and Its Impact on Consumers", to find out the degree of Internet usage of travelers and tourists as well as their preferences in online advertising. The data for the study have been collected through issue of questionnaire. A sample of 225

online users have been collected by adopting Convenient Sampling Technique. Tools like Percentages, Frequencies and Chi - Square tests are applied to analyse the data. He finds that, there is a relationship with age and their propensity of booking online and also the majority of travelers city social rewrite.

Khongkok Wei, Therera Jerome and Heongwaishan (2010), in their study on, "Online Advertising: A Study of Malaysian Consumers", aims to examine the impact of online advertising features on purchase intentions. The required data for the study have been collected only primary through issue of questionnaire. A sample of 150 customers have been collected by adopting random sampling technique. Tools like Reliability test and Regression Weights in model are used to the analysis the data. They find that, the encourage advertisers to increase their efforts regarding the Pictures feature in online advertisements.

Gresi sanje and Isil senol (2012) in their study on " An impact of Online Behavioral advertising for online retailers", aims to develop an understanding about the relationship between online shopping and online behavioral advertising. The required data for the study have been collected in primary through issue of questionnaires. The sample of 122 student studying in Istanbul bilgi university have been collected. Tools like ANOVA, Standard Deviation and Correlation are adopted to analyse the data. They find that, the customer have a positive attitude towards online shopping, since they find it time saving.

Statement of the Problem:

As companies are spending large amount on the advertisement because they want to keep their product at the top of the customer's mind. Advertisement has proven to be a successful tool for the communication but companies are still in the confusion that what kind of ingredients should be there and how do these advertisements will help to change the consumer buying behavior.

Many of the internet users are not taking advantage of the opportunities afforded by the internet, to purchase what they need, simple because they considered the products and services to be expensive and alien to their culture.

In this connection, it is induced me to rise the following questions.

- ✓ How people behave with towards online advertisements?
- ✓ Does online advertisement influence the customer's perception?

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To know the Socio Economic profile of the customer.
- ✓ To know the level of customers perception on online advertisements.

Significance of the Study:

This present study helps in exploring the impact of online advertisement on customer behavior, It is understood that advertisement is not only use for awareness about the product and services it also play an important role in purchase intention, selection option and preference towards the products. Moreover the study will help whether the direct or indirect advertising can improve the organization. It is a matter of fact that all the companies spend a lot of money on advertisements to establish the product in market as well as brand .It is also important for the companies to know how the customers are benefited with online advertisement.

Methodology:

This study made an attempt to find out the impact of online advertising on consumer buying behaviour. The study area is Pollachi taluk and required data for the study has been collected in primary through issue of questionnaire. Sample of 250 customers are selected by adopting convenient sampling technique. The statistical tools like Simple percentage and Chi-square test have been used to analyse the data.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study restricted to Pollachi Taluk alone.
- ✓ The Result cannot be generalized.

Findings of the Study:

Table 1: Demographic Profile

S.No	Determinants	No of Respondents (N=250)	Percentage (%)
1	Area of Residence		
	Rural	177	70.8
	Urban	73	29.2
2	Age		
	Below 20 years	167	66.8
	21-30 years	81	32.4
	Above 30 years	2	0.8
3	Gender		
	Male	80	32.0
	Female	170	68.0
4	Marital Status		
	Married	30	12.0
	Unmarried	220	88.0

S.No	Determinants	No of Respondents (N=250)	Percentage (%)	
5	Educational Qualification			
	Upto HSC	19	7.6	
	Diploma	11	4.4	
	UG	154	61.6	
	PG	25	10.0	
	Professional	41	16.4	
6	Occupational Status			
	Agriculturist	14	5.6	
	Businessman	40	16.0	
	Student	157	62.8	
	Employee	32	12.8	
	Professional	7	2.8	
7	Type of Family			
	Joint	65	26.0	
8	Status in the family	Nuclear	185	74.0
		Head	63	25.2
9	Earning members in the Family	Member	187	74.8
		Below 2 members	105	42.0
9	Earning members in the Family	2-3 members	143	57.2
		Above 3 members	2	0.8
		Non-Earning members in the Family		
10	Non-Earning members in the Family	Below 2 members	57	22.8
		2-3 members	179	71.6
		Above 3 members	14	5.6
11	Monthly income Customers			
	Up to Rs.10,000	119	47.60	
	Rs.10,001 - Rs.20,000	91	36.40	
	Rs.20,001 - Rs.50,000	34	13.60	
	Above Rs.50,000	6	2.40	
12	Family monthly income			
	Up to Rs.25,000	128	51.2	
	Rs.25,001 - Rs.50,000	81	32.4	
	Rs.50,001 - Rs.1,00,000	36	14.4	
	Above Rs.1,00,000	5	2.0	
13	Source of information			
	Television	73	29.2	
	Internet	80	32.0	
	Social media	31	12.4	
	Radio	6	2.4	
	Mobile Phone	60	24.0	
14	Purpose of watching online advertisement			
	To know about the product specification	146	58.4	
	To see the celebrity	22	8.8	
	To know about the brand image	40	16.0	
	Large capacity information	32	12.8	
	To know updated products	10	4.0	
15	Notice while Watching online advertisement			
	Quality	79	31.6	
	Price	74	29.6	
	Image of Product	32	12.8	
	Advertisement	21	8.4	
	Offers	44	17.6	
16	Online advertising is more convenient than traditional			

S.No	Determinants	No of Respondents (N=250)	Percentage (%)
	advertising	145	
	Yes	105	58.0
	No		42.0
	Total	250	100.0

It could be seen from the table that the most of the customers, the majority of 177 (70.8%) customers residing in rural area. The majority of 167 (66.8%) customers age is below 20 years. Majority of 170 (68.0%) customers are female. The majority of 220 (88.0%) customers are unmarried. The Majority of 154 (61.6%) customers are under graduates. Majority of 157 (62.8%) customers are students. The majority of 185 (74.0%) customers belonging to nuclear family. The Majority of 187 (74.8%) customers are member status in their family and the Majority of 143 (57.2%) customers having 2-3 earning members in their family.

The majority of 179 (71.6%) customers family belonging to 2-3 members non- earning category. Most of 119 (47.6%) customers monthly income is below Rs. 10,000 and the majority of 128 (51.2%) customers family income is up to Rs.25,000. Most of 80(32.0%) customers came to know about online advertising through internet. The majority of 148 (58.4%) customers watching online advertisement to know the product specification. Most of 79 (31.6%) customers are notice the quality of products while watching online advertisement and the majority of 145 (58.0%) customers said that the online advertising is more convenient than tradition advertising.

Level of Perception on Online Advertising:

Table 2: Demographic Profile and Level of Perception on Online Advertising

S.No	Variables	D.f	Calculated χ^2 Value	Table value	Result
1	Area of Residence	2	2.696	5.991	Not Significant
2	Age	4	22.392	9.488	Significant
3	Gender	2	6.611	5.991	Significant
4	Marital Status	2	4.681	5.991	Not Significant
5	Educational Qualification	8	40.841	15.507	Significant
6	Occupational Status	10	26.175	18.307	Significant
7	Type of Family	2	0.675	5.991	Not Significant
8	Status in the family	2	1.191	5.991	Not Significant
9	Earning member in the Family	4	9.008	9.488	Not Significant
10	Non Earning members in the Family	4	5.488	9.488	Significant
11	Monthly income	6	14.295	12.592	Significant
12	Family monthly income	6	9.874	12.592	Not Significant
13	Source of information	8	6.301	15.507	Not Significant

However, as the calculated χ^2 value is greater than the table at five per cent level, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore it is concluded that there is a significant association between age, gender, educational qualification, occupational status, Non Earning members in the Family, Monthly income of the respondents and level of perception on online advertising.

Suggestions:

- ✓ A few measures have been suggested to customer perception on online advertisement to the customers.
- ✓ The customers should not close the advertisement tap without watching full advertisement.
- ✓ The number of companies advertising online is soaring, but even then fraud and deception may reduce consumer confidence. So, they should be ensured that products and services are described truthfully in online advertisements.
- ✓ The company should provide the online the advertisement as meaningful for their product
- ✓ The companies should avoid long duration video ads, because they may customer leave to watching your advertisement.
- ✓ The company should not show the vague advertisement, the customer may watch with family members.

Conclusion:

However, Internet shopping business cannot survive without understanding the mechanism of customers repurchase intention. Hence, the E-advertisement (Web based advertisement) has not been overlooked among the marketers. The main focus of this study was to identify the factors that influence the customers buying behavior and also to know the level of customers perception on online advertisement, we have considered area of residence, age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, occupation, type of family, status in the family, monthly income of customers, family monthly income and source of information are the variables influencing the level of perception of customers on online advertising.

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